

FORMATION OF TEXT CREATION SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The article provides recommendations on the methods used by primary school students to solve problems in literacy and text creation.

As far as we know, literacy training is a very complex process and takes 4 months. First graders may not be able to master the same process. Some students learn quickly, while others lag behind.

The literacy process is divided into two stages:

Pre-alphabetic preparation period. (2 weeks) 2. Alphabet period (lasts until December 31).

In the pre-alphabet preparation period, children get acquainted with the school, classroom, discipline, teaching aids, speech development exercises and phonemic awareness.

1. The pre-alphabetic preparation period is divided into two stages:

1. Non-letter learning stage (1 week);

2. Vowel and letter learning stage (1 week);

1. The non-literacy stage is the process of working on students' connected

speech based on special copies. In addition to composing a story based on the pictures in the Alphabet, they will be told poems, fairy tales, stories, accelerations, proverbs, and riddles. Students will be introduced to notebooks and writing lines, and will be taught to write letter elements.

2. Vowels and letters are taught at the stage of learning vowels and letters.

II. Alphabet period. This is the period. Until December 31, students will be introduced to all the vowels and consonants in the alphabet. We also learned about the stages of the literacy process. During this 4-month phased process, both primary school teachers and our students face a number of challenges.

Because first graders spend a lot of time playing in kindergarten or at home, it can be difficult to sit in class and listen to a lesson. You just have to be more discriminating with the help you render toward other people.

Creating a real "miracle" in the design of the classroom gives good results. Each teacher should prepare a booklet with fairy-tale characters in each room, make large letters out of different colored paper and hang them on the classroom curtains.

In the first stage of preparation for the alphabet, oral concepts are given based on pictures. In the process, children get bored quickly because the receiving part of the brain shuts down in 20 minutes. No matter how much the teacher explains, it is natural for students not to accept it. It is advisable to take a 10-minute break every 20 minutes.

I. During the break you can ask and answer questions on the following topics:

1. About the colors of flowers;
2. About your favorite fruits;
3. Birds 4. Favorite food 5. Poetry

recitation

II. Say the opposite: the teacher says they will find the opposite word by saying the first word. For example: black and white, good-bad, day-night, hot-cold, etc.

III. "Find it" game: the children are told to clap when they say the names of the things they eat. The teacher spends a lot of time talking about school supplies, furniture, and natural objects. For example: pomegranate, honey, pineapple, fig, banana, quince, hawthorn, stream, stone. This is how it will continue. It keeps students from getting bored and keeps them focused.

In the second stage of the pre-alphabet preparation period, vowels and letters are taught.

a) Not to be hindered in pronunciation. At first, all the children pronounce it together, and asking separately gives good results. Students

pronounce and learn differently. Individual work is very important in the process of literacy for 1st graders.

b) to tell at length. Individual performance gives good results.

c) Only sound formation. First of all, all the children pronounce it together, it is necessary to ask separately. Some children may not be able to pronounce it correctly enough to pronounce it correctly.

It needs to be reworked.

Alphabetical. Continuing until December 31, students will be introduced to all the vowels and consonants in the alphabet.

Here are some suggestions on how to look or get an appointment for literacy training:

1. "Find the letter". For a student on a piece of cardboard, he mixes the familiar and unfamiliar letters learned, finds the letters o, a, n, m, u, says which letter it is, and writes it on the board.

2. Fill in the table of joints. Whatman writes on a piece of paper every day the teacher writes down the links. Every day the children study together. Then each student is taught individually. In this way, children see and understand how words are formed. Easy to remember.

This will make it easier to read.

1. Encourage students to keep notebooks from the alphabet lesson. They learn to copy the letters of the alphabet in writing.

2. Holiday Word Game. The game is played in groups. Can be arranged between rows. The first student says the word, and the second child quickly finds the word that starts with the last letter of the word his or her classmate said.

This method can be used in the native language in the third quarter. That is, the word you find can be written on the board.

Teaching literacy in primary school is a complex process that takes 4 months. In order to achieve good results and high efficiency, the methods recommended in the article can be used in pedagogical activities. lib serves.

Use of interactive methods in primary school.

"A person's thinking and intellectual potential is a social asset. They determine the socio-economic development of any society. We have children who, in the process of general secondary education, demonstrate their talents and abilities in a certain area. It is necessary to use this wealth wisely, to direct it in the right direction, I.A.Karimov said in his book "Dream of harmoniously developed generation".

Mother tongue, mathematics, reading, etiquette, science lessons in primary school have a special place in the education system due to their nature, goals and objectives. Because they are based on the basics of literacy and moral education. Therefore, special attention should be paid to increasing the interest of students in primary education. Because children should not be tired of the sacred word "lesson" from primary school. Today, experienced teachers use a variety of didactic games to increase students' interest in the lesson. The interactive method is aimed at ensuring the development of personal qualities, ensuring the acquisition of knowledge under the influence of their interaction by increasing the activity between teachers

and students in the educational process. The use of these methods increases the quality and effectiveness of the lesson. helps to increase. Its main criteria are informal debates, free expression of educational material, independent reading, study, seminars, opportunities for students to take the initiative, small group, large group, Assignments, assignments, written assignments, etc. to work as a class team.

Interactivity is the interaction of two people, that is, the learning process takes place in the form of a dialogue (computer connection) or on the basis of interaction between teachers and students. Interaction - interaction, movement, effectiveness, occurs in student-teacher, student-student conversations. The main purpose of interactive methods is to create the most favorable environment and conditions for the learning process, to create an environment for active, free, creative thinking of the student, to use his needs, interests, inner potential. Such lessons are held in such a way that in the process, no student is left out, and has the opportunity to openly express their views on what they have heard, read and seen. There is a process of mutual exchange of views. Children become more interested in learning, develop friendly relations.

Interactive learning is characterized by the use of heuristic (thinking, searching, finding) conversations through didactic games - methods of implementation of information and communication technologies on a creative basis through the creation and solution of problem situations by designing the lesson process. includes z.

Education based on information and communication technologies, in turn,

includes computer-assisted learning, distance learning, Internet-based learning, media-learning methods. Methods based on the design of heuristic conversations through didactic games are widely used in primary education according to the age characteristics of students, their level of literacy, personal nature. If in the process of teaching each student took assignments at the level of his / her ability, he / she would ensure high quality and efficiency. This can only be done through differentiated education. Now let's think about the implementation of educational processes through didactic games: Interactive game methods are based on the activation and acceleration of student activity. They play an important role in identifying and implementing practical solutions for the realization and development of creative potential of the student.

The main types of interactive games are: intellectual and mobile, as well as mixed games. They help students to develop mental, physical, moral, spiritual, educational, psychological, aesthetic, artistic, entrepreneurial, creative, labor, professional skills. This method leads the student to use his inner potential, to think, to think freely, to communicate, to be creative. In particular, it increases the interest in learning about the environment, life, the difficulties encountered, how to overcome obstacles and develop critical thinking skills. In the process of education, it is advisable to use interactive didactic games, which increase the motivation of students to learn, their abilities and interests in different areas, show a tendency to a profession. Interactive games are divided into theoretical, practical,

physical, role, business and other types. They develop students' analysis, calculation, measurement, construction, testing, observation, comparison, inference, independent decision-making, group or independent team work, speech development, language teaching and learning. According to the general theory of games, the classification of all available types of games is divided into functional, thematic, constructive, didactic, sports and military games. The following criteria will give good results in the selection of interactive games. - Games for participants, ie for boys, girls or mixed groups:

- by the number of participants - singles, pairs, small groups, large groups, class teams, inter-class and group games:

- game-based thinking, thinking, resourcefulness, action-based, competition-oriented, etc.;

- by time norm - a lesson, a part of the training time allocated according to the plan, games that last until the goal of the game is achieved, the winners are determined. All this serves to develop students' understanding of the scientific basis of the structure of the universe and the formation of scientific worldviews, the development of creative thinking by teaching student's interdisciplinary connections. has a special place in the education system? Because it is based on literacy and moral education. Therefore, the teaching of other subjects cannot be imagined without reading instruction.

The student encounters the text for the first time in reading lessons by reading the text correctly, quickly, comprehensibly, and mastering the content. Reading lessons allow students to acquire the learning skills and knowledge required to master the

requirements of the State Education Standard (SES). It is in the teaching of reading that a person is motivated, first of all, to understand himself and the world.

To this end, the textbooks include various topics such as Mother Nature, the world around us, the history and present of our country, the lives of adults and children, hard work, independence and national-spiritual values, friendship and peace. artistic, ethical-educational, scientific-popular works are intended to give a comprehensive understanding of the topics.

If reading lessons are organized in the form of introducing students to syllables, words and phrases during reading literacy and reading them, narrating them on the basis of pictures, reading after mastering the reading technique is specific. on the basis of selected artistic, scientific and popular texts on the topics.

Certain topics included in the Primary Reading book are designed to

introduce students to the magical world of fiction and to shape their worldviews based on the ideology of national independence. The leading feature of the lessons is aimed at educating students in the spirit of high moral values on the basis of national ideology, while ensuring the literacy of students.

The range of topics covered in the primary school reading lessons is much wider, covering topics such as Mother Nature, the seasons, folklore, love of work, major holiday dates, national independence and spirituality. combined within themes.

The topics chosen for the reading lessons are intended to provide students with knowledge and education on daily life, strengthening independence, and human relationships as well. The themes of independence, homeland, spirituality and nature stand out. Their goal is to awaken feelings of identity, independence, homeland and nature.

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